

Supplementary tables and figures for “Reassessing genetic relationships of *Homo heidelbergensis* among primates based on mitochondrial and nuclear DNA”

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Supplementary Table 1. Frequency of the 12 SNPs in the human genome based on calculations of Guo and Jamison (2005) and the analysis of the dbSNP database.

SNP	dbSNP	Guo and Jamison
A>C	4.7%	4.4%
A>G	16.4%	16.6%
A>T	4.1%	3.7%
C>A	4.5%	4.4%
C>G	4.2%	4.7%
C>T	16%	16.6%
G>A	16%	16.6%
G>C	4.2%	4.7%
G>T	4.5%	4.4%
T>A	4.1%	3.7%
T>C	16.4%	16.6%
T>G	4.7%	4.4%

Supplementary figure 1. Two-dimensional MDS plot of 36 primate species plus *M. domestica* as an outlier.

Supplementary figure 2a. Treemap showing the frequency of the twelve different SNP types for five ERR samples with reads from *H. heidelbergensis* mapping to hg38.

Supplementary figure 2b. Treemap showing the frequency of the twelve different SNP types for five ERR samples with reads from *H. heidelbergensis* mapping to the Neanderthal genome.